

EFFECT OF EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN CHILDREN WITH INHERITED HEMOLYTIC ANEMIA

Humaria Kanwal¹, Maria Mubarak², Khursheed Rehman³, Amjad Ali^{*4}

¹MSN Vice Principal, Al Ain Institute of Medical Health Sciences, Gujranwala

²BSN Nursing Lecturer, Shalamar Nursing College

³MSN, BSN, DNE, DNM, RN Principal, Assistant Professor, Super College of Nursing, Bahawalpur

^{*4}MSN, BSN Assistant Professor, Shalamar College of Nursing, Lahore

¹humairaqasim3355@gmail.com, ²mariamubarak098@gmail.com, ^{*4}amjadkmu233@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14874084>

Keywords

Educational Intervention, Quality of Life, Inherited Hemolytic Anemia

Article History

Received on 07 January 2025

Accepted on 07 February 2025

Published on 15 February 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the impact of educational intervention on the quality of life of children diagnosed with inherited hemolytic anemia, focusing on improvements in knowledge, health practices, and overall well-being.

Methods: An experimental design was conducted at children hospital Lahore, involving caregivers of children diagnosed with inherited hemolytic anemia. The educational intervention comprised structured sessions focusing on understanding the disease, its management, and strategies to enhance the quality of life for affected children. A two group's base study was conducted using standardized measures to assess its impact on the child's quality of life.

Results: The research revealed that a substantial proportion of mothers were between the ages of 29 and 38, had completed secondary education. Furthermore, a significant number of affected children were in the 1-3 age range, mostly boys. The intervention group (10.83±1.669). Regarding child quality of life, the control group scored (52.48±11.228), whereas the interventional group scored (70.13±11.279), with a p-value less than 0.05.

Conclusion: Improved caregiver knowledge positively influences the management and quality of life outcomes for affected children, highlighting the importance of educational initiatives in chronic disease management. Further research is warranted to explore long-term impacts and sustainability of such interventions in diverse healthcare settings.

INTRODUCTION

Anemia, primarily iron deficiency anemia (IDA), affects over a quarter of the global population, with women and children under seven being the most impacted.(1). Anemia affects 43% of children under 5 globally, causing ~591,000 perinatal deaths annually, with iron deficiency accounting for half of cases. Other causes include hemoglobin production issues, G6PD deficiency, erythrocyte damage, and blood loss.(2). Inherited hemolytic anemia, caused by

genetic mutations, leads to premature red blood cell destruction, causing fatigue, breathlessness, and jaundice. (3). Inherited hemolytic anemia includes types like sickle cell anemia, thalassemia, and hereditary spherocytosis, all causing anemia via premature red blood cell destruction (4). Hereditary anemias, involving over 70 RBC-related genes, are diverse disorders with complex genotype-phenotype links, recently better understood genetically. (5). In

2010, ~312,000 children were diagnosed with anemia caused by a β -chain hemoglobin mutation, substituting glutamic acid with valine. (6). G6PD deficiency, a genetic red blood cell disorder affecting 4.5% globally, impacts 400 million people, with high prevalence in Africa, Asia, the Mediterranean, and Latin America (7).

However, this analysis overlooked several locally published non-indexed papers reporting an incidence of 2% to 4% in Pakistani males, with a high incidence of 8% in Pathans (8). Two significant national studies found that 26% and 30% of all hospital admissions, respectively, in 1624 and 6454 babies required evaluation of neonatal jaundice. Important contributors to jaundice were identified as low birth weight, ABO or Rh incompatibility, and sepsis, while G6PD deficiency was found in 8% of jaundiced babies (9).

Genetic testing for G6PD deficiency identifies carriers, aiding management and prevention, especially in high-prevalence populations. (10). Genetic testing diagnoses G6PD deficiency in symptomatic individuals, enabling targeted interventions to prevent hemolysis-related complications. (11). Genetic testing informs family planning by assessing G6PD deficiency inheritance risks and enabling options like prenatal testing. (10). Genetic testing helps develop targeted public health strategies for managing G6PD deficiency through education, counseling, and screening in high-prevalence areas. (12).

Neonatal G6PD deficiency screening raises awareness, enabling early treatment and reducing mortality and morbidity. (13). G6PD deficiency, an inherited hemolytic anemia, affects children's quality of life, requiring ongoing medical care and caregiver support for well-being (14). Caregiver knowledge of hemolytic anemia improves early symptom recognition, treatment adherence, and emotional support, enhancing the child's quality of life. (15). Exploring caregivers' knowledge of hemolytic anemia can identify support needs and improve children's quality of life through better care and education (16). Knowledgeable caregivers can identify early complications, seek timely medical care, and implement preventive measures to support a child's health with hemolytic anemia.(17). Knowledgeable

caregivers ensure children with hemolytic anemia receive the correct medication dosage on time to manage symptoms and prevent complications. (18).

The effective management of G6PD deficiency anemia relies on the knowledge of caregivers regarding the triggers that can initiate hemolysis. Caregivers who possess adequate knowledge of the disease can ensure that affected children live a healthy life. Since children are unable to take care of themselves, the responsibility lies on caregivers to ensure they understand the disease and provide appropriate care at home. The knowledge of caregivers can have a significant impact on the quality of life and frequency of hospitalization for children with G6PD deficiency anemia. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the relationship between caregiver knowledge and the quality of life and frequency of blood transfusions in children with G6PD deficiency anemia at a public hospital in Lahore.

Materials And Methods: This study used a randomized controlled design to assess the impact of an educational intervention on children's quality of life related to G6PD disease. The independent variable was the educational intervention, and the dependent variable was children's quality of life. Child quality of life was evaluated using the Pediatric Quality of Life (PedsQoL) Generic Core Scales, with scores <50 indicating poor quality of life and >50 indicating good quality of life. The study was conducted at the Children Hospital in Lahore over nine months, with 46 participants (23 in the control group and 23 in the intervention group). Data collection occurred in three phases: pre-intervention, during the intervention (which involved educational sessions), and post-intervention. The educational intervention focused on educating caregivers about G6PD deficiency, including triggers, symptom recognition, medication management, dietary guidance, and emotional support. Ethical guidelines were followed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity. Data analysis involved using SPSS, with normality tests and statistical tests like paired t-tests and independent t-tests to analyze differences within and between groups.

Results:

Table No 1: Demographic variables of the study participants

Demographic Variables		n	%
Mother Age	18 - 28	21	45.7
	29- 38	25	54.3
Mothers' education	Illiterate	16	34.8
	Primary	13	28.3
	Secondary	17	37.0
Mothers' occupation	Housewife	17	37.0
	Working	29	63.0
Residence	Urban	26	56.5
	Rural	20	43.5
Positive kin relationship between the couples	Yes	15	32.6
	No	31	67.4
Positive family history for G6PD deficiency	Yes	12	26.1
	No	34	73.9
Child age in Year	1-3 Years	28	60.9
	4- 7 Years	14	30.4
	8-10 Years	4	8.7
Child Gender	Male	24	52.2
	Female	22	47.8
Valid Blood Transfusion Frequency	Weekly	14	30.4
	Monthly	17	37.0
	Bimonthly	15	32.6

Analyzed by frequency (n) and percentage (%)

The study participants' demographic characteristics include mothers aged 18-28 (45.7%) and 29-38 (54.3%), with varying educational backgrounds (34.8% illiterate, 28.3% primary, 37.0% secondary). Occupationally, 37.0% are housewives, and 63.0% are working. The participants are mostly from urban areas (56.5%) with a smaller portion from rural areas (43.5%), and 26.1% have a family history of G6PD

deficiency. Children's ages range from 1-3 years (60.9%) to 8-10 years (8.7%), with a near equal gender distribution (52.2% male, 47.8% female), and blood transfusions occur weekly (30.4%), monthly (37.0%), or bimonthly (32.6%) as shown in the table 1.

Table no 2: Quality of life among children with inherited hemolytic anemia

	n	%	X	S.D
<50 or 50% Poor Quality of life	27	58.7	45.54	12.354
>50 or 50% Good Quality of life	19	41.3		

Descriptive statistics mean (X) and standard deviation (S.D)

The data shows that 59% of children with inherited hemolytic anemia (27 children) have a poor quality of life, scoring below 50%, while 41% (19 children) have a good quality of life, scoring above 50%. The average score is 45.54, with a standard deviation of

12.354, indicating considerable variability in the children's quality of life. This provides an overview of the diverse quality of life outcomes among these children as shown in the table 2.

Table 3: Pre Quality of life among children with inherited hemolytic anemia

	n	X	S.D	P-value
Control Group	23	42.13	12.903	0.06
Interventional Group	23	48.96	11.228	

Analyzed by independent t test with a p less than 0.05

The pre-quality of life scores for children with inherited hemolytic anemia show that the Control Group (23 participants) has an average score of 42.13 with a standard deviation of 12.903, while the Interventional Group (23 participants) has an average score of 48.96 with a standard deviation of

11.228. An independent t-test yielded a p-value of 0.219, indicating no significant difference between the two groups. This data offers insights into the pre-intervention quality of life levels and the potential impact of interventions as shown in the table 3

Table no 4: Post Quality of life among children with inherited hemolytic anemia

	n	X	S.D	P-value
Control Group	23	52.48.96	11.228	0.000
Interventional Group	23	70.13	11.279	

Analyzed by independent t test with a p less than 0.05

The post-quality of life scores for children with inherited hemolytic anemia show that the Control Group (23 participants) has an average score of 52.49 with a standard deviation of 11.228, while the Interventional Group (23 participants) has a significantly higher average score of 70.13 with a

standard deviation of 11.279. An independent t-test yielded a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance. These results suggest a significant improvement in the well-being of children in the Interventional Group as shown in the table 4.

Table 5: Quality of life among children with inherited hemolytic anemia parallel group

	Pre		Post		P-value
	X	S.D	X	S.D	
Control Group	42.13	12.903	52.48.96	11.228	0.057
Interventional Group	48.96	11.228	70.13	11.279	0.001

Analyzed by paired t test with a p less than 0.05

This data compares the quality of life in children with inherited hemolytic anemia before and after an intervention. The Control Group showed a slight improvement from 42.13 to 52.49 (p = 0.057), while the Interventional Group's score increased

significantly from 48.96 to 70.13 (p < 0.05). Paired t-test analysis revealed significant differences between the groups, suggesting the intervention had a notable positive impact on the children's quality of life as shown in the table 5

Table no 6: Impact of educational interventional on caregiver Quality of life

Quality of life	Control Group	Interventional Group	Mean difference	P-value
	X+S.D	X+S.D		
Pre-test	42.13.+12.903	48.96+11.04	+6.83	0.06
Post-test	52.48+11.228	70.13+11.279	+17.65	0.000

Analyzed by independent t test with a p less than 0.05

Table 6 compares the impact of an educational intervention on caregivers' quality of life. The Control Group had an average score of 52.48, while the Interventional Group, which received the intervention, had a significantly higher score of 70.13. An independent t-test ($p < 0.05$) revealed a highly significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.000$), indicating the educational intervention greatly improved caregivers' quality of life.

Discussion: The study found that 54.3% of mothers were aged 29-38, 37% had secondary education, and 63% were employed, with 56.5% residing in urban areas. Additionally, 60.9% of children were aged 1-3 years, 52.2% were boys, and 37% required monthly blood transfusions, with 26.1% having a family history of G6PD deficiency. Similarly the study of Gehan and colleague study found that out of the total thalassemia patients, 67.2% were boys with age between 8 and 18 years (19). Saqladi and Albanna's study found that 8.8% of individuals received blood transfusions, 63.4% of whom were male, with an average age of 5 years. (20). Additionally, half of the transfused children were aged ≤ 5 years old (20).

The present study revealed that the concept of quality of life encompasses various dimensions and is typically comprised of subjective assessments of both favorable and unfavorable aspects of life (21). The study found that 84.8% of participants had poor knowledge (below 50%), while 59% of children with inherited hemolytic anemia had a poor quality of life (below 50%), and 41% had a good quality of life (above 50%). In contrast research by Ramadan and colleagues found that 72.5% of patients demonstrated a satisfactory level of knowledge about thalassemia, with 27.5% having an unsatisfactory level. Concerning quality of life, 22.5% of patients reported a good level, while 77.5% indicated a poor level. However, no statistically significant relationship was observed between the overall knowledge level and the quality of life among thalassemia patients, with a p-value of 0.6 (22).

Essawy and Colleagues found that most children with sickle cell anemia had poor (66%) or neutral (23%) quality of life, with only a small percentage reporting a good quality of life. Poor quality was linked to procrastination, pain, and limited physical

activity. Notably, 95.5% of children exhibited poor quality of life due to procrastination. (23).

The study suggests a direction for future research, as demonstrated by Mardhiyah and Colleagues which revealed a positive association between family management practices and the quality of life of children with thalassemia. This underscores the significance of educating families about efficient management strategies. (24). The current study compared the impact of an educational intervention on caregivers' quality of life between a Control Group and an Interventional Group. Initial quality of life scores averaged 52.48 with a standard deviation of 11.228 for the Control Group, whereas the Interventional Group, receiving the intervention, had a higher average score of 70.13 with a standard deviation of 11.279.

Mohammed and Abdalla's study found significant improvements in knowledge, practices, and quality of life for mothers and children with beta-thalassemia after a health coaching intervention. The program led to better outcomes for both mothers and their children.(25). A quasi-experimental study showed that children with sickle cell anemia improved from poor to moderate quality of life after using the precede-proceed planning model (26).

Grace and colleagues emphasized the importance of understanding patients' perceptions of living with Pyruvate kinase deficiency. They suggested developing tools to assess patient-reported symptoms and explore how interventions affect health-related quality of life.(27). Mayih and colleagues found no significant link between socio-demographic factors and self-care dimensions, though adolescents with major thalassemia showed high self-care scores, particularly in emotional, social, and spiritual self-care. They recommend further investigation and patient education to improve self-care in chronic conditions (28).

The studies highlight the need for rigorous evaluation of educational interventions to assess changes in knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. This helps measure their impact and identify areas for improvement (29). Educational interventions are essential for improving awareness and practices around health conditions like iron deficiency anemia,

G6PD deficiency, and favism. Tailored approaches considering demographics and culture are key to better outcomes, with ongoing research needed for effectiveness.

Conclusion: The study revealed key findings: many mothers aged 29-38 years have secondary education and employment, while most affected children are aged 1-3 years, with boys being the majority. Many children require monthly blood transfusions, highlighting the severity of their condition. The study emphasizes the importance of education in managing conditions like anemia and G6PD deficiency, and found a significant improvement in quality of life following the educational intervention ($p = 0.000$). This highlights the vital role of education in enhancing well-being and the need for continued efforts in this area.

REFERENCE

1. Rosenthal P, Alrabadi L. Neonatal Hepatitis and Congenital Infections. In: Suchy FJ, Sokol RJ, Balistreri WF, editors. *Liver Disease in Children*. 5 ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2021. p. 147-61.
2. Riaz M, Abbas M, Rasool G, Baig IS, Mahmood Z, Munir N, et al. Prevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections in multiple blood transfusion-dependent thalassemic patients in Asia: A systemic review. *International Journal of Immunopathology and Pharmacology*. 2022;36:03946320221096909.
3. Pivina L, Semenova Y, Doşa MD, Dauletyarova M, Bjørklund G. Iron deficiency, cognitive functions, and neurobehavioral disorders in children. *Journal of Molecular Neuroscience*. 2019;68(1):1-10.
4. Aliyo A, Jibril A. Assessment of anemia and associated risk factors among children under-five years old in the West Guji Zone, southern Ethiopia: Hospital-based cross-sectional study. *Plos one*. 2022;17(7):e0270853.
5. Russo R, Marra R, Rosato BE, Iolascon A, Andolfo I. Genetics and genomics approaches for diagnosis and research into hereditary anemias. *Frontiers in Physiology*. 2020;11:613559.
6. Gebreweld A, Ali N, Ali R, Fisha T. Prevalence of anemia and its associated factors among children under five years of age attending at Gugufu health center, South Wollo, Northeast Ethiopia. *PloS one*. 2019;14(7):e0218961.
7. Rizwan N, Kaleemi S, Kareem S, Chaudary SS, Zafar S, Syed S. Etiological Profile of Hereditary Hemolytic Anemia among Patients Presenting in Tertiary Care Hospital of Lahore. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023;17(03):103.
8. Tariq R, Mahmud T, Bashir S, Akhtar S, Israr M. Impact Of Population Screening Programs On The Knowledge, Attitudes And Practices Regarding Prevention Of Thalassemia. *Pakistan BioMedical Journal*. 2021;4(2):209-14.
9. Majid H, Jafri L, Ahmed S, Humayun K, Kirmani S, Ali NB, et al. Perspective on newborn screening (NBS): Evidence sharing on conditions to be included in NBS in Pakistan. 2022.
10. Hamodi LE, Naji AS, Ismael SH. factors associated with anemia in women of reproductive age in iraqi females sample. *Age*. 2022;14(19):20-9.
11. Chordiya K, Katewa V, Sharma P, Deopa B, Katewa S. Quality of Life (QoL) and the Factors Affecting it in Transfusion-dependent Thalassemic Children. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2018;85(11):978-83.
12. García Maset L, Santillán Garzón S, Ortega López P. Adolescent with Alport syndrome and congenital hemolytic anemia. *Nefrología (English Edition)*. 2023;43(1):146-7.
13. Dogar AW, Ullah K, Ghaffar A, Ud-din S, Hussain A, Ahmed HB, et al. Safety of glucose-6 phosphate dehydrogenase deficient donors in living right lobe liver donation. *Clinical Transplantation*. 2022;36(6):e14627.
14. Hakeem GLA, Mousa SO, Moustafa AN, Mahgoob MH, Hassan EE. Health-related quality of life in pediatric and adolescent patients with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia in upper Egypt (single center

- study). *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*. 2018;16(1):59.
15. Amer HW, Zaghamir DE, Ayed MM. Effect of Webinar educational program on Mothers' Knowledge and Practices regarding iron deficiency anemia among their Children. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*. 2021;9(25.0):1-11.
 16. Vaghela PT. A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding prevention of iron deficiency anemia among the primigravida mother in selected Hospital Mehsana. *International Journal of Nursing Education and Research*. 2020;8(4):488-91.
 17. Salia SM, Afaya A, Wuni A, Ayanore MA, Salia E, Kporvi DD, et al. Knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding neonatal jaundice among caregivers in a tertiary health facility in Ghana. *PloS one*. 2021;16(6):e0251846.
 18. Dhabangi A, Idro R, John CC, Dzik WH, Opoka R, Siu GE, et al. Caregivers and community perceptions of blood transfusion for children with severe anaemia in Uganda. *Transfusion Medicine*. 2019;29(1):61-7.
 19. Hakeem GLA, Mousa SO, Moustafa AN, Mahgoob MH, Hassan EE. Health-related quality of life in pediatric and adolescent patients with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia in upper Egypt (single center study). *Health and quality of life outcomes*. 2018;16:1-9.
 20. Al-Saqladi A-WM, Albanna TA. A study of blood transfusion in pediatric patients at a Teaching Hospital, Aden, Yemen. *International Journal of Clinical Transfusion Medicine*. 2021:1-9.
 21. Sii-Felice K, Giorgi M, Leboulch P, Payen E. Hemoglobin disorders: lentiviral gene therapy in the starting blocks to enter clinical practice. *Experimental hematology*. 2018;64:12-32.
 22. Ramadan Korany N, Sayed Ali H, Abd ELRahman Abd ELRahman A, ELAshery Ashery R. Relationship between Knowledge of Patients with Thalassemia and their Quality of Life. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*. 2022;13(4):612-25.
 23. Essawy MA, El Sharkawy A, Al Shabbani Z, Aziz A. Quality of life of children with sickle cell anemia. *IOSR J Nurs Health Sci*. 2018;7:29-39.
 24. Mardhiyah A, Panduragan SL, Mediani HS, Yosep I. Nursing Interventions to Improve Quality of Life Among Children and Adolescents with Thalassemia: A Scoping Review. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*. 2023:1749-62.
 25. Mohammed YA, Abdalla AI. Effect of Health Coaching Intervention on Mothers' Performance and Quality of Life of their Children with Beta Thalassemia. *Assiut Scientific Nursing Journal*. 2022;10(31):43-56.
 26. Elkholy SA, Elbahnasawy HT, Fathala AA, Amal A, Ahmed HM. Application of PRECEDE-PROCEED Planning Model on Quality of Life among Children with Sickle Cell Anemia. *Menoufia Nursing Journal*. 2022;7(2):73-90.
 27. Grace RF, Cohen J, Egan S, Wells T, Witherspoon B, Ryan A, et al. The burden of disease in pyruvate kinase deficiency: patients' perception of the impact on health-related quality of life. *European journal of haematology*. 2018;101(6):758-65.
 28. Mayih Dakhil M, Shirinabadi Farahani A, Nourian M, Nasiri M, Babaie M. Quality of Self-Care in Adolescents with Major Thalassemia Referred to Selected Thalassemia Centers in Iran. *Health Education and Health Promotion*. 2023;11(4):1001-7.
 29. Kasad K, Keumalahayati K, Azwarni A, Harahap MS, Helmi A. The effect of the family empowerment model on the ability to managing diet and increasing hemoglobin in pregnant women. *AcTion: Aceh Nutrition Journal*. 2023;8(4):675-82.